

Studies on Electrolysis in a W-tube with Reference to Non-Faradaic Behaviour*

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Electrolysis of a dilute aqueous solution at low current density in a W-tube, though associated with high volume deficit, is nearly free from coliberation; its occurrence, if at all, being limited to the anode gas only. Unlike the electrolysis in a U-tube, two sharp and stationary boundaries formed in the intermediate zone of the W-tube may act as barriers to the migration of the ions responsible for the non-Faradaic phenomenon of coliberation.

It was observed by Palit^{1,2} that if an alcoholic solution of an ionic dye or a dilute aqueous solution of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ is electrolysed in a double-bent U-tube (called a W-tube), two very sharp boundaries appear inside the two inner tubes, dividing the solution into three zones as: anode - acidic dark coloured - neutral colourless - alkaline light coloured - cathode. Such phenomenon in a W-tube was also observed later by other workers³. Since electrolysis in a W-tube shows such intriguing features (depletion in the intermediate zone in violation of Hittorf mechanism of current conduction), it was considered interesting to examine the extent to which the W-tube shows non-Faradaic behaviour^{4,5}. The earlier observations on non-Faradaic electrolysis were confined to U-tube only. The results reported in this paper also show the effect of cell geometry on non-Faradaic electrolysis.

Experimental

The W-tube used for the electrolysis is shown in Fig. 1. Electrodes used are bright platinum foils

Fig. 1.

(1 cm²). Like U-tubes⁶, the arms of the W-tube are also connected to gas burettes for collection of the liberated gases at the anode and the cathode. A coulometer containing 1.0 N K_2SO_4 solution was connected in series. Current was passed either from D. C. mains (230 volts) or D. C. power supply unit. At the beginning, 2 mA current was allowed to pass but with the progress of electrolysis, the current density decreased to a very small value (a few hundred μA) due to depletion of ions from the middle portion of the W-tube. The electrolysis was, therefore, allowed to run for several days so that a measurable amount of gas could be collected over the electrodes. Liberated gases were then analysed by sparking with the help of a tesla coil.

Results and Discussion

The results are given in Fig. 2 and they are discussed with a comparison with those obtained in a U-tube under otherwise identical conditions.

(i) *Electrolysis of salt solution (0.001 N)*: With dilute solution of sodium sulphate or potassium sulphate, the results become very much different from those in a U-tube and the salient features are:

- High volume deficit (less than 50% of the total gas is liberated) and almost no coliberation on either side. Small amount of gas is evolved at the intermediate zone of the cell.
- Current falls to a very low value with the progress of electrolysis because the ions gradually get removed from the middle portion of the tube.

0.001 N $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution also does not give coliberation on either side but the deficit is not as high as with potassium or sodium sulphate solution.

Electrolysis of 0.01 N Na_2SO_4 solution gives completely Faradaic results which is also very unlikely during electrolysis in a U-tube.

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Fig. 2. Results of electrolysis in a W-tube. Of the three jointed columns, the left one (dotted) represents the total volume of gases liberated, the middle one the volume of gas at the cathode, and the right one that at the anode. The striped and the darkened parts in the middle and the right columns represent the volume of hydrogen and oxygen respectively in the mixture of the two.
 a = 0.001 N NaOH at cathode and distilled water at anode, b = Distilled water at cathode and 0.001 N H₂SO₄ at anode, c = 0.001 N NaOH at cathode and 0.001 N H₂SO₄ at anode.

(ii) *Electrolysis of water*: With pure water, the volume deficit, though very high, is less than what is found with the salt solutions and a remarkable observation is that the anode gas explodes on sparking while the cathode gas remains totally free of coliberation.

(iii) *Electrolysis of 0.001N sulphuric acid solution*: At the beginning when some acid still remains near the cathode, no coliberation takes place on either side. With progress of electrolysis, as the acid concentration at the cathode side diminishes, the anode gas explodes on sparking while the cathode gas is pure hydrogen. However, the percentage of coliberation at the anode side is not very high.

(iv) *Electrolysis of 0.001 N sodium hydroxide*: Results are similar to those observed in the experiment with 0.001 N H₂SO₄.

(v) *Electrolysis of two different electrolytes at the cathode and the anode*: Few experiments were done by using alkali/acid, water/acid or alkali/water separately in the two compartments.

(a) (C) *alkali-acid (A)*: With 0.001 N NaOH at the cathode side and 0.001 N H₂SO₄ at the anode side, the results are similar to those obtained with 0.001 N salt solutions. There is no coliberation either at the cathode gas or at the anode gas and volume deficit is also very high.

(b) (C) *water-acid (A)*: Distilled water at the cathode side and 0.001 N H₂SO₄ at the anode side

give results different from those in the previous set up. The anode gas remains explosive while the cathode gas is free from any coliberation. Volume deficit is not very remarkable.

(c) (C) *alkali-water (A)*: Results similar to those in set up (b) are obtained with 0.001 N NaOH at the cathode side and distilled water at the anode side.

Conclusion: So far, the results with U-tube led us to believe that electrolysis at low current density and low concentration always produces non-Faradaic features, particularly deficit and coliberation. The results with W-tube brings forth the inadequacy of the above tenet. Here is a cell geometry where, though the current density and the concentration are both low, the deficit is extraordinarily high but there is no coliberation of the cathode gas in almost all cases, and whatever coliberation there is, it is limited only to the anode gas. These features are probably connected with boundary formation as is observed with many dyes. Since electrolysis in a W-tube shows a very intriguing behaviour mainly formation of two sharp and stationary boundaries separating the solutions into three zones: A/acid-water-alkali/C, it may be assumed that the intermediate zone somehow acts as a barrier to the ions which are responsible for the coliberation at cathode. If we presume these ions to be H₃O⁺, they are likely to get discharged at the centre with production of some H₂O₂. This explains why in such experiments the

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hydrogen-oxygen stoichiometry is unbalanced in favour of hydrogen. The observations reported in this paper also lend support to the contention* that water getting charged at the electrodes and carrying a part of the current is responsible for non-Faradaic behaviour.

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